

A new flavone glycoside from the seeds of *Cassia sophera* Linn.

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Abstract : A new flavone glycoside A, m.p. 248-251 °C, C₃₃H₄₀O₂₀, [M]⁺ 756 (FABMS) has been isolated from methanol soluble fraction of defatted seeds of *Cassia sophera* Linn. alongwith a known compound B, 5-hydroxy-7,4',5'-trimethoxyisoflavone-3'-O-β-D-glucopyranoside. Compound A was characterized as, 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-3-methoxy flavone-5-O-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-7-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl(1→3)-O-β-D-xylopyranoside by various colour reactions, chemical degradations and spectral analysis.

Keywords : *Cassia sophera* Linn., Leguminosae, flavone glycoside.

Cassia sophera Linn.^{1,2} (Leguminosae) is commonly known as 'Kasundi' or 'Banar' in Hindi. It is a shrub or under shrub 2.4-3 m high, annual or perennial. It is distributed throughout India and in most tropical countries. Its bark and seeds are useful in diabetes. Its leaves are used externally in ringworm. Decoction of plant is used in acute bronchitis. Its bark, leaves and seeds are used as cathartic.

Earlier workers^{3,4} have reported the presence of various constituents from this plant. In view of the aforementioned medicinal properties and absence of any previous systematic phytochemical investigation, it was thought worthwhile to carry out further phytochemical examination of this plant. In the present paper, we report the isolation and structural elucidation of a new flavone glycoside 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-3-methoxy flavone-5-O-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-7-O-β-D-glucopyranosyl(1→3)-O-β-D-xylopyranoside from the seeds of this plant alongwith a known compound B, 5-hydroxy-7,4',5'-trimethoxyisoflavone-3'-O-β-D-glucopyranoside.

Results and discussion

The methanol fraction of the defatted seeds of the plant afforded a novel compound A, m.p. 248-251 °C, empirical composition C₃₃H₄₀O₂₀ and [M]⁺ 756 (FABMS). It responded Molisch and Shinoda tests⁵ showing its flavonoidal glycosidic nature. Its IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 3350 (br) (-OH), 3010 (C-H aromatic), 2949 (C-H saturated), 2870 (-OMe), 1640 (>C=O), 1625 (aromatic ring system), 1230, 1100, 830

cm⁻¹. Its UV spectrum with various shift reagents suggested the presence of free hydroxyl group at C-3' and C-4' positions. The ¹H NMR spectrum of A showed two singlets at δ 6.45 and 6.70, which were assigned to H-6 and H-8 respectively. The signals at δ 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz), 7.64 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 1.7 Hz) and 7.30 (1H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz) are assignable to H-2',6',5' respectively. The anomeric proton signals at 5.18 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz), 5.00 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz) and 4.90 (1H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz) were assigned to H-1'', H-1''' and H-1'''' of L-rhamnose, D-xylose and D-glucose respectively.

Acid hydrolysis of compound A with ethanolic-H₂SO₄ (10%) gave aglycone A₁, m.p. 182-184 °C, composition C₁₆H₁₂O₇, [M]⁺ 316 (EIMS) which was identified as 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-3-methoxy flavone by comparison of its spectral data with reported literature values⁶⁻⁸.

The aqueous hydrolysate, after the removal of aglycone, was neutralized with BaCO₃ and BaSO₄ filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subjected to PC

A₁

and sugars were identified as D-glucose (R_f 0.19), D-xylose (R_f 0.27) and L-rhamnose (R_f 0.36). Periodate oxidation of compound A, confirmed that all the sugars were present in the pyranose form⁹.

The positions of sugar moieties in compound A were determined by permethylation¹⁰ followed by acid hydrolysis which yielded methylated aglycone identified as 5,7-dihydroxy-3,3',4'-trimethoxy flavone and methylated sugars identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose, 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,4-di-*O*-methyl-D-xylose (by co-PC), according to Petek¹¹ sugar moieties were attached to C-5 and C-7 positions of aglycone. It was further confirmed by ¹³C NMR spectra (see Experimental section).

Enzymatic hydrolysis of A with takadiastase liberated L-rhamnose and proaglycone (C), confirming the presence of a linkage between L-rhamnose and proaglycone. Proaglycone (C) on further hydrolysis with almond emulsin liberated D-glucose first followed by D-xylose and aglycone, suggesting the presence of β -linkage between D-glucose and D-xylose as well as between D-xylose and aglycone.

Proaglycone (C) obtained after the enzymatic hydrolysis of compound A with takadiastase (C₂₇H₃₀O₁₆), m.p. 237–238 °C, [M]⁺ 610 (FABMS). By comparing its mass spectral data with compound A, suggested that proaglycone didn't have rhamnose unit. Its UV spectrum showed bathochromic shift of 45 nm¹² with AlCl₃ relative to MeOH in band I, indicating the presence of free -OH group at C-5 position in proaglycone. There was no bathochromic shift in band II with NaOAc, indicating the absence of free -OH group at C-7 position. Proaglycone showed bright yellow colour with boric acid in presence of citric acid¹³ and green colour with aqueous ferric chloride¹⁴. These colour reactions further confirmed that L-rhamnose was attached at C-5 position in compound A.

Permethylation of proaglycone followed by acid hydrolysis gave methylated aglycone identified as 7-hydroxy-3,5,3',4'-tetramethoxy flavone and methylated sugars identified as 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,4-di-*O*-methyl-D-xylose (by co-PC). Therefore it was concluded

that C-1''' of D-glucose was linked with C-3'' of D-xylose and C-1'' of D-xylose attached to C-7 position of aglycone. Proaglycone on further hydrolysis with almond emulsin liberated D-glucose (R_f 0.19) first followed by D-xylose (R_f 0.27) and aglycone, suggesting the presence of β -linkage between D-glucose and D-xylose as well as between D-xylose and aglycone. Thus the structure of proaglycone was characterised as 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-3-methoxyflavone-7-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)-*O*- β -D-xylopyranoside.

On the basis of above evidences, the structure of compound A was characterized as 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-3-methoxy flavone-5-*O*- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-7-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 3)-*O*- β -D-xylopyranoside.

Compound B was analysed for molecular formula C₂₄H₂₆O₁₂, m.p. 140–141 °C. It was identified as 5-hydroxy-7,4',5'-trimethoxyisoflavone-3'-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside by comparison of its spectral data (UV, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, MS) with the reported values¹⁵.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined on a thermoelectrical melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr disc, ¹H NMR spectra at 300 MHz in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal standard, ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at 90 MHz using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent; UV spectra were determined in MeOH and mass spectra on a Jeol SX-102 mass spectrometer.

The seeds of *Cassia sophera* were procured from M/s United Chemicals and Allied Products, Kolkata and were taxonomically authenticated by the Department of Botany, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar (M.P.), India. A voucher specimen has been deposited in the Natural Products Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar (M.P.), India.

Air-dried powdered seeds (3 kg) of the plant were extracted with petroleum ether (40–60 °C) in a Soxhlet apparatus for seven days. The defatted seeds successively extracted with C₆H₆, CHCl₃, CH₃COOCH₃, CH₃COCH₃ and methanol. The methanol soluble fraction of the plants was concentrated under reduced pressure which showed two spots on TLC examination using solvent system CHCl₃ : MeOH (4 : 6) indicating it to be a mixture of A and B. These compounds were separated by TLC and purified by column chromatography over silica gel.

Study of compound A :

It had m.p. 248–251 °C, m.f. C₃₃H₄₀O₂₀, [M]⁺ 756

Note

(FABMS); found (%) : C 52.35, H 5.23, calcd. (%) : C 52.38, H 5.29; UV (MeOH) λ_{\max} (nm); 251, 270, 335, (+AlCl₃) 251, 272, 357, (+AlCl₃-HCl) 252, 270, 357, (+NaOAc) 252, 272, 337, (+NaOAc-H₃BO₃) 252, 271, 353. IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹); 3450 (OH gp), 3010 (C-H aromatic), 2949 (C-H saturated), 2870 (OMe), 1640 (>C=O), 1625 (aromatic ring system), 1525, 1230, 1100, 1060, 870, 830; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm); 3.90 (3H, s, OMe), 6.50 (1H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz, H-6), 6.68 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-8), 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz, H-2'), 7.30 (1H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz, H-5'), 7.64 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 1.6 Hz, H-6'), 5.18 (1H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, H-1''), 4.80 (1H, dd, *J* 3.8, 10.0 Hz, H-2''), 4.76 (1H, dd, *J* 3.8, 10.0 Hz, H-3''), 4.58 (1H, dd, *J* 3.7, 10.0 Hz, H-4''), 4.21 (1H, m, H-5''), 1.28 (3H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, H-6''), 5.00 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, H-1'''), 4.41 (1H, dd, *J* 3.7, 10.0 Hz, H-2'''), 4.12 (1H, dd, *J* 3.8, 10.0 Hz, H-3'''), 4.17 (1H, m, H-4'''), 4.40 (2H, d, *J* 6.4, H-5'''), 4.90 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, H-1'''), 3.80 (1H, dd, *J* 3.8, 10.0 Hz, H-2'''), 3.78 (1H, dd, *J* 3.8, 10.0 Hz, H-3'''), 3.54 (1H, dd, *J* 3.8, 10.0 Hz, H-4'''), 4.01 (1H, m, H-5'''), 4.40 (2H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz, H-6'''); ¹³C NMR (90 MHz DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm); 158.5 (C-2), 140.3 (C-3), 180.1 (C-4), 163.2 (C-5), 104.0 (C-6), 164.7 (C-7), 97.5 (C-8), 158.9 (C-9), 108.8 (C-10), 124.2 (C-1'), 116.5 (C-2'), 145.3 (C-3'), 150.4 (C-4'), 117.8 (C-5'), 123.8 (C-6'), 100.7 (C-1''), 77.4 (C-2''), 77.0 (C-3''), 76.8 (C-4''), 69.1 (C-5''), 20.1 (C-6''), 102.8 (C-1'''), 74.1 (C-2'''), 73.0 (C-3'''), 71.0 (C-4'''), 69.6 (C-5'''), 107.2 (C-1'''), 72.6 (C-2'''), 71.0 (C-3'''), 72.8 (C-4'''), 69.0 (C-5'''), 63.5 (C-6'''); MS : (FABMS) *m/z*, 756 [M]⁺ (absent), 610 [M⁺-rhamnose], 594 [M⁺-glucose], 462 [M⁺-glucose-xylose], 316 [aglycone], 301, 288, 153, 152, 134, 124, 110.

Acid hydrolysis of compound A :

125 mg of compound A was dissolved in ethanol (30 ml) and refluxed with 20 ml of 10% H₂SO₄ on water bath for 8-10 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated and allowed to cool and residue was extracted with diethyl ether.

The ethereal layer was washed with water and the residue was chromatographed over silica gel using CHCl₃ : MeOH (4 : 6) to give compound A₁, which was identified as 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-3-methoxy flavone by comparison of its known spectral data. The aqueous hydrolysate was neutralized with BaCO₃ and BaSO₄ filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination using n-BAW [4 : 1 : 5] and

sugars were identified as D-glucose (*R_f* 0.19), D-xylose (*R_f* 0.27), L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.36).

Study of compound A₁ :

It had m.f. C₁₆H₁₂O₇, m.p. 182-184 °C, [M]⁺ 316 (EIMS); found (%) : C 60.78, H 3.81; calcd. (%) : C 60.75, H 3.79; IR (KBr) ν (cm⁻¹); 3450, 3010, 2949, 2875, 1640, 1620, 1525, 1060, 870 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm); 3.85 (3H, s, OMe), 6.51 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-6), 6.72 (1H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-8), 7.70 (1H, d, *J* 1.6 Hz, H-2'), 7.27 (1H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, H-5'), 7.62 (1H, dd, *J* 1.6, 8.0 Hz, H-6'); ¹³C NMR (90 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ (ppm); 158.1 (C-2), 140.3 (C-3), 180.0 (C-4), 164.8 (C-5), 102.8 (C-6), 166.0 (C-7), 96.6 (C-8), 160.0 (C-9), 107.3 (C-10), 124.2 (C-1'), 116.6 (C-2'), 145.3 (C-3'), 150.4 (C-4'), 117.8 (C-5'), 123.7 (C-6'); MS : (FABMS) *m/z*, 316 [M]⁺, 315, 300, 287, 299, 298, 284, 153, 152, 134, 124, 110.

Permethylation of compound A :

Compound A (50 mg) was refluxed with MeI (5 ml) and Ag₂O (40 mg) in DMF (60 mg) for one day and then filtered. The filtrate was hydrolysed with 10% ethanolic H₂SO₄ for 7-8 h to give methylated aglycone identified as 5,7-dihydroxy-3,3',4'-trimethoxy flavone and methylated sugars which were identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose, 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and 2,4-di-*O*-methyl-D-xylose.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of compound A :

The compound A (25 mg) was dissolved in MeOH (25 ml) and hydrolysed with equal volume of Takadiastose at room temperature in a 150 ml round bottomed flask fitted with air condenser. The contents were left for 2 days and filtered. The proaglycone C and hydrolysate were studied separately.

The hydrolysate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination using n-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) solvent system which showed the presence of L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.36) (co-PC).

The proaglycone (50 mg) was dissolved in MeOH (40 ml) and hydrolysed with equal volume of almond emulsin. The reaction mixture was allowed to stay at room temperature for 2 days and filtered. The aglycone was identified as 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-3-methoxy flavone. The hydrolysate was concentrated and studied by paper chromatography examination using n-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) solvent system and aniline hydrogen phthalate as spraying reagent. The sugars were identified as D-glucose (*R_f* 0.19) and D-xylose (*R_f* 0.27) (co-PC).

Study of proaglycone C :

It had m.f. $C_{27}H_{30}O_{16}$, m.p. 237–238 °C, [M] 610 (FABMS); found (%) : C 53.09, H 4.95; calcd. (%) : C 53.11, H 4.92; UV (MeOH) λ_{max} (nm); 250, 270, 336, (+AlCl₃) 250, 272, 381, (+NaOAc) 252, 271, 337, (+NaOAc+H₃BO₃) 250, 271, 353; MS : (FABMS) *m/z*, 610 [M]⁺, 448 [M⁺-glucose], 316 [M⁺-glucose-xylose], 301, 288, 150, 134, 124, 110.

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